

The Parameter Planes of the Spherically Symmetric and Static Relativistic Solutions for Polytropes

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Abstract

We explore the parameter space of the family of static and spherically symmetric solutions of the Einstein field equations for polytropes, that were presented in a previous paper. This is a four-parameter family of exact solutions, of which one parameter can be factored out, so that there are only three essential free parameters. The solutions are exact in the sense that no approximations are involved, other than those implied by the numerical precision limitations. The primary objectives of this exploration are to establish directly the existence of large collections of specific solutions, and to determine some of their most important properties.

For each value of one of the three essential free parameters of the family of solutions, the polytropic index n , taken here, for the sake of simplicity, to be either an integer or a half-integer, we define and explore the parameter planes spanned by the other two essential free parameters. In this way, besides establishing their existence, we are also able to classify the solutions according to their overall matter energy density, as well as in terms of their proximity to solutions that display an event horizon.

For four values of n we successfully establish the allowed regions of the parameter planes, where the solutions not only exist but also correspond to physically acceptable matter. We find that there are solutions within these regions with overall matter energy densities varying all the way from very low to very high, including some that are as close as one may wish to solutions that display an event horizon, and that therefore represent black holes, or extremely dense objects very similar to them.

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1 Introduction

In a previous paper [1] we established the static solution of the Einstein field equations for the case of spherically symmetric shells of gaseous fluid located between radial positions r_1 and r_2 of the Schwarzschild system of coordinates. These solutions are exact in the sense that they involve no approximations, but they are not written entirely in closed analytical form. While all relevant functions describing both the geometry and the matter are written analytically in terms of a single function, which we denote by $\beta(r)$, and although the main properties of this function can also be established analytically, it is still necessary to determine this function in detail by numerical means, including the existence of the internal and external radii r_1 and r_2 , and therefore the existence of the solution itself.

In this paper we will present a fairly extensive numerical exploration of the parameter space of these solutions, in order to establish the general picture in regards to their existence and to their main properties. Connections with some special cases which are already well known will be pointed out. Some diagnostic observables will be defined and calculated, which were designed to put in evidence some of the most important properties of the solutions. In this paper we will be limited to the case in which the polytropic index n , which is one of the free parameters, is *strictly* larger than 1, that is, satisfies $n > 1$.

This paper is organized as follows: in Section 2 we review the new class of static and spherically symmetric exact solutions for gaseous shells; in Section 3 we discuss the parameter planes for a few values of the polytropic index n , and examine in particular the allowed regions in each case; in Section 4 we discuss the definition and the behavior of the diagnostic observables over the allowed regions, and thus establish the general character of the solutions; in Section 5 we discuss in general terms how to apply the solutions to problems in astrophysics; in Section 6 we provide some further analysis of the solutions; and in Section 7 we state our conclusions.

2 Review of the Polytropic Solutions

In this section we will review the solutions for gaseous fluids presented in [1], in order to establish the notation, as well as the most basic character of the solutions. Both the notation and the ideas presented in [1] rely on some of the notation and ideas presented in the previous paper [2], in which we presented the exact solution for the case of liquid fluids. In this work we will use the time-like signature $(+, -, -, -)$, following [3]. In terms of the coefficients of the metric, for a static invariant interval given in terms of the Schwarzschild coordinates (t, r, θ, ϕ) by

$$ds^2 = e^{2\nu(r)} c^2 dt^2 - e^{2\lambda(r)} dr^2 - r^2 [d\theta^2 + \sin^2(\theta) d\phi^2], \quad (1)$$

where $\exp[\nu(r)]$ and $\exp[\lambda(r)]$ are two positive functions of only r , the Einstein field equations reduce to the set of three first-order differential equations

$$\left\{ 1 - 2 [r\lambda'(r)] \right\} e^{-2\lambda(r)} = 1 - \kappa r^2 \rho(r), \quad (2)$$

$$\left\{ 1 + 2 [r\nu'(r)] \right\} e^{-2\lambda(r)} = 1 + \kappa r^2 P(r), \quad (3)$$

$$[\rho(r) + P(r)] \nu'(r) = -P'(r), \quad (4)$$

where $\rho(r)$ is the energy density of the matter, $P(r)$ is its isotropic pressure, and the constant κ is given by $\kappa = 8\pi G/c^4$, where G is the universal gravitational constant and c is the speed of light. In these equations the primes indicate differentiation with respect to r .

It is convenient for the analysis of the solutions to change variables in the field equations from the function $\lambda(r)$ to a function $\beta(r)$, which is defined to be such that

$$e^{2\lambda(r)} = \frac{r}{r - r_M \beta(r)}, \quad (5)$$

where $r_M = 2GM/c^2$ is the Schwarzschild radius associated to the total asymptotic gravitational mass M , which then implies that we have for the corresponding derivatives

$$2r\lambda'(r) = -r_M \frac{\beta(r) - r\beta'(r)}{r - r_M \beta(r)}. \quad (6)$$

Substituting the expressions in Equations (5) and (6) in the component field equation shown in Equation (2) a very simple relation giving the derivative of $\beta(r)$ in terms of $\rho(r)$ results,

$$\beta'(r) = \frac{\kappa r^2 \rho(r)}{r_M}. \quad (7)$$

Therefore, in any interval where $\rho(r) = 0$ we have that $\beta(r)$ is a constant. Since we must have that $\rho(r) \geq 0$, it therefore follows that $\beta(r)$ is a monotonically increasing function, which is a constant if and only if we are within a vacuum region. In addition to this, since according to the asymptotic boundary condition we must have that $\beta(r) \rightarrow 1$ when $r \rightarrow \infty$, it also follows that $\beta(r)$ is limited from above by 1.

In the previous paper [1] we established the static solution of the Einstein field equations for the case of a spherically symmetric shell of gaseous fluid located between the radial positions r_1 and r_2 of the Schwarzschild system of coordinates. These positions are *not* arbitrary, but rather are obtained as part of the solution of the problem. For this problem we assume the hypothesis that the gas satisfies the polytropic equation of state

$$P(r) = K [\rho(r)]^{1+1/n}, \quad (8)$$

where K , the polytropic constant, is a positive real constant, and $n > 1$, the polytropic index, is a real number that, merely for simplicity, may be taken to be an integer or half-integer. For convenience we define the auxiliary quantity

$$F(r) = K [\rho(r)]^{1/n}, \quad (9)$$

in terms of which the equation of state becomes simply

$$P(r) = F(r)\rho(r). \quad (10)$$

Given the field Equations (2) through (4) and the equation of state shown in Equation (8), the solution is given by

$$\lambda(r) = \begin{cases} -\frac{1}{2} \ln\left(\frac{r + r_M}{r}\right) & \text{for } 0 < r \leq r_1, \\ -\frac{1}{2} \ln\left[\frac{r - r_M \beta(r)}{r}\right] & \text{for } r_1 \leq r \leq r_2, \\ -\frac{1}{2} \ln\left(\frac{r - r_M}{r}\right) & \text{for } r_2 \leq r < \infty, \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

$$\nu(r) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2} \ln\left(\frac{1 - r_M/r_2}{1 + r_\mu/r_1}\right) + \frac{1}{2} \ln\left(\frac{r + r_\mu}{r}\right) & \text{for } 0 < r \leq r_1, \\ \nu(r_2) - (n+1) \ln[1 + F(r)] & \text{for } r_1 \leq r \leq r_2, \\ \frac{1}{2} \ln\left(\frac{r - r_M}{r}\right) & \text{for } r_2 \leq r < \infty. \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

The solution introduces into the system the new physical parameter r_μ with dimensions of length, which can be associated to a mass parameter μ by $r_\mu = 2G\mu/c^2$. The determination of the function $\beta(r)$ in the matter region leads to the determination of all the functions that describe both the matter and the geometry of the system within that region, by means of

$$\rho(r) = \frac{r_M \beta'(r)}{\kappa r^2}, \quad (13)$$

$$P(r) = K \left[\frac{r_M \beta'(r)}{\kappa r^2} \right]^{1+1/n}, \quad (14)$$

$$F(r) = K \left[\frac{r_M \beta'(r)}{\kappa r^2} \right]^{1/n}, \quad (15)$$

$$\lambda(r) = \frac{1}{2} \ln \left[\frac{r}{r - r_M \beta(r)} \right], \quad (16)$$

$$\nu(r) = \nu(r_2) - (n+1) \ln[1 + F(r)]. \quad (17)$$

This also determines the solutions within the inner and outer vacuum regions, which depend only on r_μ and r_M , through the interface boundary conditions at r_1 and r_2 . The four free parameters of the system are K , n and M , all of which describe the nature and state of the matter, and the value of $\beta'(r)$ at its point of maximum, which can also be seen to be related to the matter, since it determines the general scale of the matter energy density, as can be seen from Equation (7).

For all sets of parameters for which there is a solution of the differential problem the function $\beta'(r)$ has a single point of maximum within the matter region, which is the point where $\beta(r)$ has its single inflection point. For all existing solutions with $r_1 > 0$ it holds that $r_\mu > 0$, which implies that $\beta(r)$ has a single zero within the matter region. The strictly positive value of r_μ implies that the solutions have singularities at the origin. However, although the singularity has the invariant character of a curvature singularity, it has also a repulsive rather than attractive character, and thus is not associated to an infinite concentration of matter, but rather to exactly zero matter energy density around that point.

Both for the subsequent analysis and for the numerical approach, it is convenient to further transform variables at this point, in order to write everything in terms of dimensionless variables and functions. In order to do this we must now introduce an arbitrary radial reference position $r_0 > 0$. This mathematical device allows us to define a dimensionless radial variable and a dimensionless parameter associated to the mass M by

$$\xi = \frac{r}{r_0}, \quad (18)$$

$$\xi_M = \frac{r_M}{r_0}, \quad (19)$$

as well as to define the dimensionless function of ξ , meant to assume the role of $\beta(r)$,

$$\gamma(\xi) = \xi_M \beta(r). \quad (20)$$

The (C, π_e) Parameter Plane for $n = 1.5$

Figure 1: The (C, π_e) parameter plane for the case $n = 1.5$. The Tooper curve approaches the origin as an integer power, namely as C^3 . The limiting curve is given by $\pi_e = 1/C^{1.5}$.

The functions $\gamma(\xi)$ and $\beta(r)$ are both determined by the second-order ordinary differential equation

$$\pi'(\xi) = \pi(\xi) \left\{ \frac{2}{\xi} - \frac{n}{n+1} \frac{1}{\xi - \gamma(\xi)} \frac{1 + F(\xi, \pi)}{2F(\xi, \pi)} \left[\frac{\gamma(\xi)}{\xi} + F(\xi, \pi)\pi(\xi) \right] \right\}, \quad (21)$$

where $\pi(\xi) = \gamma'(\xi)$ is the derivative of $\gamma(\xi)$, the primes now indicate derivatives with respect to ξ , and $F(\xi, \pi)$ is given by

$$F(\xi, \pi) = C \left[\frac{\pi(\xi)}{\xi^2} \right]^{1/n}, \quad (22)$$

where $C = K/(\kappa r_0^2)^{1/n}$ is a dimensionless constant associated to the polytropic constant K . This differential system can be interpreted as a pair of first-order coupled ordinary differential equations determining $\gamma(\xi)$ and $\pi(\xi)$, the other equation being simply

$$\gamma'(\xi) = \pi(\xi). \quad (23)$$

This pair of first-order ordinary differential equations can be used for the numerical integration of this differential system, in order to obtain $\gamma(\xi)$ and $\beta(r)$. In terms of these dimensionless variables the equation of state shown in Equation (8) can be written as

$$\bar{P}(\xi) = C [\bar{\rho}(\xi)]^{1+1/n}, \quad (24)$$

where we define the dimensionless pressure and energy density by

The (C, π_e) Parameter Plane for $n = 2.0$

Figure 2: The (C, π_e) parameter plane for the case $n = 2.0$. The Tooper curve approaches the origin as an integer power, namely as C^2 . The limiting curve is given by $\pi_e = 1/C^{2.0}$.

$$\bar{P}(\xi) = \kappa r_0^2 P(\xi), \quad (25)$$

$$\bar{\rho}(\xi) = \kappa r_0^2 \rho(\xi). \quad (26)$$

Relation in Equation (7), when written in terms of the dimensionless variables, becomes

$$\pi(\xi) = \xi^2 \bar{\rho}(\xi). \quad (27)$$

Note that the mass M and the Schwarzschild radius r_M no longer appear explicitly in the equations. The mass M is a free parameter of the system that has effectively been factored out of it. Later on, in Section 5, we will see that this simply means that there are solutions for all possible values of M and r_M .

3 The Parameter Planes

We will begin by simply presenting the results of an extensive numerical exploration of the solutions, and subsequently we will discuss each element that is involved in this exploration. In their dimensionless formulation, the solutions are described by the three dimensionless free parameters n , C and $\pi_e = \pi(\xi_e)$, where ξ_e is the position of the inflection point of $\gamma(\xi)$, which is also the position of the maximum π_e of $\pi(\xi)$. For each value of n , the solutions can be classified according to a parameter plane spanned by C and π_e . We used a small discrete set of values of n , namely the values 1.5, 2.0, 2.5 and 3.0. For each one of these values we scanned the parameter planes described by the Cartesian coordinates (C, π_e) ,

The (C, π_e) Parameter Plane for $n = 2.5$

Figure 3: The (C, π_e) parameter plane for the case $n = 2.5$. The Tooper curve approaches the origin as a fractional power, namely as $C^{5/3}$. The limiting curve is given by $\pi_e = 1/C^{2.5}$.

aiming at locating the allowed regions of these parameter planes, that is, the regions where the solutions, first of all exist, and second correspond to physically acceptable matter.

In Figures 1 through 4 we present the allowed regions of the parameters planes, for the aforementioned four values of n . As one can see, the four parameter planes shown are generically quite similar. Each point in one of these graphs corresponds to a run of the numerical program [4] with the given values of n , C and π_e , as well as with the value $\xi_e = 1$ for the value of the position of the inflection point of $\gamma(\xi)$, which is the position of the extremum π_e of $\pi(\xi)$. This choice, which since we have that $\xi_e = r_e/r_0$ can be written as $r_e = r_0$, means only that from now on we choose the arbitrary parameter r_0 to be the radial position r_e of this inflection point. The runs were done on a grid with variations of C given by $\Delta C = 0.005$, starting from $C = 0.005$.

Here is the part of the description of the parameter planes which is common to all four cases. The strong solid lines represent the Tooper curves. On these curves lie the solutions found by Tooper [5] a long time ago. Over these curves we have that $\xi_1 = 0$, meaning that these solution are for filled spheres rather than for shells, and also that $\xi_\mu = 0$, which is the particular condition imposed by Tooper in order to obtain his solutions, a condition which avoids the singularity at the origin. Below these curves there are no acceptable solutions of the differential equation, since the solutions diverge when one integrates towards $\xi = 0$. Later on, in Subsection 3.4, we will examine in more detail exactly what happens in this case. Therefore, all existing solutions are necessarily above the Tooper curves.

The strong dashed lines represent the Dominant Energy Condition [6] curves (or DEC curves for short). Above these curves the stress-energy tensor of the matter does not satisfy

The (C, π_e) Parameter Plane for $n = 3.0$

Figure 4: The (C, π_e) parameter plane for the case $n = 3.0$. The Tooper curve approaches the origin as a fractional power, namely as $C^{3/2}$. The limiting curve is given by $\pi_e = 1/C^{3.0}$. The vertical lines mark the anomalous region. The crosses mark points where a divergence was detected when integrating outward, towards infinity.

this condition, so that the behavior of the matter is not physically acceptable. Note that this does not mean that the solution of the differential equation itself does not exist above these curves, since in general it does in fact exist, and can be calculated without too much trouble. It just means that there is no physically possible matter that would result in these solutions. It is verified numerically that the DEC curves are always below the limiting curves shown in the graphs, with the light dotted lines, which are given by

$$\pi_e(C) = \frac{1}{C^n}. \quad (28)$$

We will see later, between the end of Subsection 3.1 and Subsection 3.2, that the DEC curve has this same type of dependency with C . Note that this indicates that the allowed regions extend indefinitely to arbitrarily large values of π_e , always below the DEC curves, and becoming ever closer to $C = 0$. Of course, due to this we can only show a finite portion of these allowed regions in the graphs. In short, all physically acceptable solutions are necessarily below the DEC curves, as well as above the Tooper curves. It should be noted that over the $C = 0$ axis there are also no solutions, since in this case, according to the definition of C given immediately after Equation (22), we have that $K = 0$, so that according to the equation of state shown in Equation (8) we then have pressureless dust, and therefore there are no stable static solutions. Therefore all acceptable solutions must have $C > 0$, that is, *strictly* positive C . It should also be noted that, since π_e is the maximum value of the necessarily positive function $\pi(\xi)$, the $\pi_e = 0$ axis corresponds to

Log-log plot of the Tooper curves.

Figure 5: Double logarithmic graph of π_e versus C over the Tooper curves for each value of n , showing that they approach the origin as powers. So long as $n > 1$ the Tooper curves can be written as $\pi_e(C) = \alpha_n C^m$ near the origin, where $m = n/(n - 1)$.

flat, empty space, since in this case we have that $\pi(\xi) \equiv 0$, which means that $\gamma'(\xi) \equiv 0$ and hence, by Equation (20), that $\beta'(r) \equiv 0$, which in turn, by Equation (7), implies that $\rho(r) \equiv 0$ and therefore that there is no matter present at all.

The set of facts just described identifies completely the allowed regions of the solutions, for each value of n . Every solution must be above the Tooper curves, below the DEC curves, and away from the π_e axis. The small remaining gaps between the DEC and Tooper curves, seen on the extreme right of the graphs, are a consequence of the numerical difficulty when running the program in those regions. What seems to happen in these cases is that at these points the DEC curves fall off in a very sharp way, and immediately cross the Tooper curves. The effect of this is that, according to the numerical exploration performed so far, there seems to be no acceptable solutions anywhere more than a distance $\Delta C = 0.005$ to the right of these gaps. Therefore, all existing acceptable solutions must also be located to the left of these gaps. Further investigation of these small regions would be numerically expensive, and this seems to be unnecessary at this stage.

In the graphs one can also see the light dashed lines, that represent sequences of allowed solutions that constitute limits that we will describe here as *black hole limits*. What we mean by such a black hole limit is one in which the formation of an event horizon at the position r_2 of the outer interface is approached, so that the geometry everywhere outside that horizon tends to be given by the exterior Schwarzschild metric. Note that there is no matter dynamics involved in these limits, they are simply sequences of static solutions. What is being stated here is that there are static solutions, within our family of static

solutions, which are as close as one may wish to what is sometimes referred to as a naked black hole solution, at least in what concerns the region strictly outside the event horizon.

We should point out here the peculiar behavior of the case $n = 3.0$ for the larger values of C . The vertical lines seen in Figure 4 characterize the region where the behavior is quite different from all other cases. The onset of this anomalous behavior occurs approximately at $C \simeq 0.43$, and is characterized by increasingly larger values of ξ_2 as C is increased, thus leading to very long running times for the program, when integrating outward. This behavior becomes severe around $C \simeq 0.53$, with very large values of ξ_2 , that can go all the way up to 6×10^4 or more. It seems to cease after $C \simeq 0.63$.

In some cases between $C \simeq 0.53$ and $C \simeq 0.63$ the program even detects a divergence when integrating outward, which is very unusual, and was completely unexpected. This of course represents a failure to satisfy the asymptotic boundary condition, so that in this case the solution does not really exist. The points of the parameter plane where this happens are marked with small crosses in the graph. To the right of $C \simeq 0.63$ the situation seems to normalize to some extent, but still with values of ξ_2 that are significantly larger than usual.

It is uncertain whether these divergent cases are caused by the accumulation of numerical errors during very long integration runs, which could prevent the graph of $\pi(\xi)$ from hitting the ξ axis. And the opposite effect is also possible, since it is also true that in some cases the graph of $\pi(\xi)$ may in fact hit the ξ axis precisely *due* to these accumulated numerical errors. The detailed examination of this region would require a large number of very numerically expensive runs, so that for the time being a refinement of this analysis will have to wait.

Note that this anomalous behavior refers only to the outward integration. The integration inward still works in the typical way, even if the outward one diverges. This leads to partial solutions, which are valid only within finite radial intervals of ξ , from the inner interface at ξ_1 to some finite value. They just cannot be extended to radial infinity. These partial solutions may still be relevant, since they may play a role as the inner parts of multi-layered solutions. In this case they do not have to satisfy the asymptotic boundary condition at radial infinity, but rather a set of boundary conditions on an interface located at some finite value of ξ .

Finally, let us point out that the Tooper curves for $n > 1$ all approach the origin $C = 0$ of the graphs behaving like (possibly fractional) powers, as described in the figure captions. In Figure 5 one can see log-log plots of these curves for all values of n that were used. The fact that the left-hand portions of these curves tend to behave like straight lines close to $C = 0$ betrays such a power behavior, so that for each value of n we have that

$$\pi_e(C) \simeq \alpha_n C^m, \quad (29)$$

near to and to the right of the point $C = 0$, where α_n is some constant. We can abstract from the numerical data that the power m is given by

$$m = \frac{n}{n-1}. \quad (30)$$

Note that this is singular for $n = 1$ and negative for $n < 1$, indicating a profound change in the behavior of the whole system in such cases.

3.1 The Dominant Energy Condition

Since the Dominant Energy Condition (DEC) [6] is a cornerstone of the determination of the allowed regions in the parameters planes of the solutions for each value of n , let us derive the form that this condition takes for the polytropic solutions. In order to do this

we start with a preliminary discussion of the Weak Energy Condition (WEC) [6]. Let us start, then, by noting that we have for the metric tensor and for the stress-energy tensor,

$$\text{diag}[g_{\mu\nu}] = \left[e^{2\nu(r)}, -e^{2\lambda(r)}, -r^2, -r^2 \sin^2(\theta) \right], \quad (31)$$

$$\text{diag}[T_{\mu}{}^{\nu}] = \left[\rho(r), -P(r), -P(r), -P(r) \right]. \quad (32)$$

The WEC is a condition on the stress-energy tensor, namely the statement that, for all causal vector fields V^μ , it holds that

$$T_{\mu\nu}V^\mu V^\nu \geq 0. \quad (33)$$

Consider now a completely arbitrary vector field

$$V^\mu = \left(V_0, V_1, V_2, V_3 \right), \quad (34)$$

so that we get for the corresponding covariant components $V_\mu = g_{\mu\nu}V^\nu$

$$V_\mu = \left(e^{2\nu(r)}V_0, -e^{2\lambda(r)}V_1, -r^2V_2, -r^2 \sin^2(\theta)V_3 \right). \quad (35)$$

This implies that we get for $V^2 = V_\mu V^\mu$

$$V^2 = e^{2\nu(r)}V_0^2 - e^{2\lambda(r)}V_1^2 - r^2V_2^2 - r^2 \sin^2(\theta)V_3^2, \quad (36)$$

on which, for the time being, we will impose no conditions at all. Consider now the vector field W^μ defined by

$$W^\mu = T^\mu{}_\nu V^\nu. \quad (37)$$

In terms of this vector field the tensor expression in the WEC can be written as

$$T^\mu{}_\nu V_\mu V^\nu = V_\mu W^\mu, \quad (38)$$

where

$$W^\mu = \left(\rho(r)V_0, -P(r)V_1, -P(r)V_2, -P(r)V_3 \right). \quad (39)$$

Therefore the tensor expression in the WEC, which is the contraction of V^μ and W^μ , reads

$$V_\mu W^\mu = \rho(r)e^{2\nu(r)}V_0^2 + P(r)e^{2\lambda(r)}V_1^2 + P(r)r^2V_2^2 + P(r)r^2 \sin^2(\theta)V_3^2. \quad (40)$$

Since $\rho(r)$, $P(r)$, the exponentials and the squares are all positive quantities, this is a sum of positive terms, and is therefore positive. We therefore conclude that the WEC is satisfied for all vector fields V^μ , regardless of any conditions imposed on them, and in particular for all causal vector fields, given that from Equations (38) and (40) we have

$$T_\nu{}^\mu V_\mu V^\nu \geq 0, \quad (41)$$

so that the WEC is satisfied. Apparently this is a consequence of the fact that both $g_{\mu\nu}$ and $T_{\mu\nu}$ are diagonal. Since the quantity above is an invariant, this condition of course holds on all reference frames.

Let us now discuss the DEC, which once more is a condition on the stress-energy tensor. Given an arbitrary future-pointing causal vector field V^μ , consider once more the vector field given by $W^\mu = T^\mu{}_\nu V^\nu$. The DEC is the statement that, for all future-pointing causal

vector fields V^μ , the vector field W^μ is also a future-pointing causal vector field. Let us consider once more the vector field V^μ and its covariant components V_μ , but we now impose that it is a future-pointing causal vector field, with $V_0 > 0$, and hence that it also satisfy the condition

$$V^2 \geq 0, \quad (42)$$

which from Equation (36) implies that

$$\left[e^{2\nu(r)} V_0^2 \right] - \left[e^{2\lambda(r)} V_1^2 + r^2 V_2^2 + r^2 \sin^2(\theta) V_3^2 \right] \geq 0. \quad (43)$$

Let us now consider again the vector field W^μ given in Equation (39), where $W_0 = \rho(r)V_0$ is positive because $\rho(r)$ is positive and because V^μ is a future-pointing causal vector field, so that V_0 is positive. Let us recall that the DEC consists of the statement that, if V^μ is a future-pointing causal vector field, then W^μ is also a future-pointing causal vector field. Using the metric tensor we have for its covariant components

$$W_\mu = \left(\rho(r) e^{2\nu(r)} V_0, P(r) e^{2\lambda(r)} V_1, P(r) r^2 V_2, P(r) r^2 \sin^2(\theta) V_3 \right). \quad (44)$$

We now simply calculate $W^2 = W_\mu W^\mu$, and thus get

$$W^2 = \rho^2(r) \left[e^{2\nu(r)} V_0^2 \right] - P^2(r) \left[e^{2\lambda(r)} V_1^2 + r^2 V_2^2 + r^2 \sin^2(\theta) V_3^2 \right]. \quad (45)$$

Now, since V^μ is a future-pointing causal vector field we have from Equation (43) the condition for the quantities within brackets in the equation above,

$$\left[e^{2\nu(r)} V_0^2 \right] \geq \left[e^{2\lambda(r)} V_1^2 + r^2 V_2^2 + r^2 \sin^2(\theta) V_3^2 \right]. \quad (46)$$

Besides, from Equation (45) we have that the condition $W^2 \geq 0$ is equivalent to

$$\rho^2(r) \left[e^{2\nu(r)} V_0^2 \right] \geq P^2(r) \left[e^{2\lambda(r)} V_1^2 + r^2 V_2^2 + r^2 \sin^2(\theta) V_3^2 \right], \quad (47)$$

and therefore from Equation (46) we conclude that so long as $\rho^2(r) \geq P^2(r)$, and therefore so long as

$$\rho(r) \geq P(r), \quad (48)$$

we have that

$$W^2 \geq 0. \quad (49)$$

Since we also have that $W_0 > 0$, it follows that W^μ is a future-pointing causal vector field, so that the DEC is satisfied.

The question then remains of determining when we have the condition $\rho(r) \geq P(r)$ for all values of r within the matter region. Interestingly, it is fairly easy to do this in the case of the solutions for polytropes. If we assume that $\rho(r) \geq P(r)$, which is equivalent to

$$\frac{\bar{P}(\xi)}{\bar{\rho}(\xi)} \leq 1, \quad (50)$$

for the corresponding dimensionless quantities defined in Equations (25) and (26), and use the polytropic equation of state in the dimensionless form given in Equation (24), then it follows that

$$\frac{\bar{P}(\xi)}{\bar{\rho}(\xi)} = C [\bar{\rho}(\xi)]^{1/n}, \quad (51)$$

from which the DEC reduces to

$$C [\bar{\rho}(\xi)]^{1/n} \leq 1. \quad (52)$$

Recalling from Equation (27) that we have $\bar{\rho}(\xi) = \pi(\xi)/\xi^2$, the condition reduces to

$$\frac{\pi(\xi)}{\xi^2} \leq \frac{1}{C^n}. \quad (53)$$

This is the DEC for polytropes, and it must be true for all values of ξ within the matter region. It suffices therefore to impose this condition only at the point where $\bar{\rho}(\xi)$ is maximum, that is, at the point where $\pi(\xi)/\xi^2$ is maximum. However, as one can see in the figures given in [1], for $n > 1$ and the larger values of π_e , and hence of $\bar{\rho}(\xi)$, the points of maximum of $\bar{\rho}(\xi)$ and of $\pi(\xi)$ tend to coincide, as do the values of these two quantities at their points of maximum, if we use the value $\xi_e = 1$ for the point of maximum of $\pi(\xi)$, as we do here.

Therefore, if we consider the point $\xi_e = 1$, the position of the inflection point of $\gamma(\xi)$ at which we start the numerical runs, where $\pi(\xi) = \gamma'(\xi)$ has its global maximum π_e , then we see that it is a fair estimate for high-density solutions to consider the DEC curve as located approximately at this point, and thus we arrive at a simple constraint among the free parameters of the solutions, for large values of π_e and $\bar{\rho}(\xi_e)$,

$$\pi_e \leq \frac{1}{C^n}. \quad (54)$$

As it turns out, the curve given by the equality case above constitutes an upper bound to the DEC curve $\pi_e(C)$, for all values of n and all values of C , as shown in the graphs in Figures 1 through 4. For very small values of C and correspondingly very large values of π_e , these two curves tend to be close to one another. For each value of the polytropic index n , and given some value of the dimensionless polytropic constant C , the equality case in Equation (53) gives us a maximum allowed value of the parameter π_e . It therefore establishes an allowed region within the (C, π_e) parameter plane of this family of solutions. The exact relation between C and π_e for the DEC curve, given by the equality case in Equation (53), can be easily obtained by numerical means.

3.2 Determination of the DEC Curve

Here we will describe in detail how we determined the position of the DEC curve. For technical reasons, this is better done before the determination of the Tooper curve, as we will see. The program that integrates the differential system given in Equations (21) and (23) has two monitoring procedures installed within it, one for identifying a divergence during the integration, and the other to identify a violation of the DEC. This last one does its job by monitoring the quantities $\bar{P}(\xi)$ and $\bar{\rho}(\xi)$ as they are calculated, as well as the ratio $\bar{P}(\xi)/\bar{\rho}(\xi)$ of the two, which according to the DEC has to be always below 1. Whenever this ratio goes above 1, at any point ξ , the program creates a flag file to record the event. The existence of this flag file can then be used by another program in order to institute a search for the position of the DEC curve. Note that from Equation (52) the DEC can be written as

$$\bar{\rho}(\xi) \leq \frac{1}{C^n}, \quad (55)$$

thus showing that the condition can be written in terms of $\bar{\rho}(\xi)$ alone, so that this is the only quantity that we really have to monitor. Starting from the inflection point of $\gamma(\xi)$, as we will always do here, there may be violations of the DEC either when integrating inward, towards the origin, or when integrating outward, towards infinity. However, in order to search for the position of the DEC curve it suffices to integrate only inward, as shown by the following argument. Since from Equation (27) we have that

$$\bar{\rho}(\xi) = \frac{\pi(\xi)}{\xi^2}, \quad (56)$$

and since we will always start the integration from the point of maximum of $\pi(\xi)$, located at $\xi = \xi_e = 1$, where $\bar{\rho}(\xi_e) = \pi(\xi_e)$, taking a derivative of the relation in Equation (56) above with respect to ξ and applying at ξ_e we have that

$$\bar{\rho}'(\xi_e) = -2\pi(\xi_e), \quad (57)$$

given that we have that $\pi'(\xi_e) = 0$ and also that $\xi_e = 1$. Since $\pi(\xi_e)$ is a strictly positive quantity, it follows that $\bar{\rho}(\xi)$ increases when we go to the left-hand side of ξ_e and decreases when we go to the right-hand side of it. Since both $\bar{\rho}(\xi)$ and $\pi(\xi)$ are functions with a single point of maximum, it follows from this that the point of maximum of $\bar{\rho}(\xi)$ is always located to the left of the point of maximum of $\pi(\xi)$. Therefore, in order to detect a violation of the DEC, it suffices to integrate only to the left of the inflection point.

Note that this establishes the position of the maximum of $\pi(\xi)$ as an upper bound for the position of the maximum of $\bar{\rho}(\xi)$, as one can see in the graphs shown in [1]. It also explains why the limiting curve is an upper bound for the DEC curve. At the position of the inflection point we have that $\xi_e = 1$ and therefore we have from Equation (53) that the DEC reduces to $\pi(\xi) \leq 1/C^n$. Therefore, the position of the limiting curve at this point corresponds to the maximum value of $\bar{\rho}(\xi)$ that satisfies the DEC at this point. However, when we go to the left, thus decreasing ξ below the value 1, according to the argument above the graph of $\bar{\rho}(\xi)$ will raise above the limiting curve $1/C^n$, thus violating the DEC, and hence we will have to decrease the value of $\pi(\xi_e)$ in order to make the whole function $\bar{\rho}(\xi)$ fall below the DEC limit. Therefore, the value of $\pi(\xi)$ at the DEC curve is always below its value at the limiting curve.

3.3 Algorithm for the DEC Curve

Let us now describe in detail how we determined the position of the DEC curve. For each value of n the determination of the DEC curve starts at the lowest value of C for which one wishes to include the DEC curve in the graph. At that point we start the search at the value of π_e given by the limiting curve, which is always above the DEC curve,

$$\pi_e = \frac{1}{C^n}. \quad (58)$$

We then integrate the differential system only to the left, towards the origin, expecting to find a violation of the DEC at this initial point of the search. Once the violation is detected at any point ξ we abort the integration, decrease the value of π_e by a certain variation $\Delta\pi_e$, and repeat the integration. This proceeds until a violation of the DEC is no longer detected, meaning that we are now below the DEC curve. Once this happens we return π_e

A Run Below the Tooper Curve.

Figure 6: All the functions obtained from a trial solution of the differential equation with parameters below the Tooper curve. The integration diverges when one integrates towards the origin. The left vertical line marks the initial point of the integration to either side, and the right vertical line marks the position of ξ_2 as obtained by the integration to the right side. The parameters used were $n = 1.5$, $C = 1/3$, $\xi_e = 1.0$ and $\pi_e = 0.5$.

to its previous value, decrease the variation $\Delta\pi_e$ by some constant factor, and continue the downward search for the position of the DEC curve.

This results in a fast exponential search for the position of the DEC curve, since the variation $\Delta\pi_e$, which represents the distance between the position of the search and the position of the DEC curve, decreases exponentially fast. Note that we can start with a rather large value of $\Delta\pi_e$, since it will be decreased exponentially fast. We chose to start with $\Delta\pi_e = 0.1$. The stop criterion for this downward search is the condition that the addition of $\Delta\pi_e$ to π_e no longer change π_e , meaning that the relative precision represented by $\Delta\pi_e/\pi_e$ falls below the precision level at which the search program runs. Since that program runs in double precision mode (64-bit word), this guarantees the localization of the DEC curve within that double precision level. Naturally the precision of the results of the search is also affected by the precision with which the differential system is integrated. The integration code runs in quadruple precision mode (128-bit word), and we chose to use an integration interval of $\Delta\xi = 10^{-5}$. Since the integration program uses the Runge-Kutta fourth-order integration algorithm, this results in an excellent level of precision, certainly much greater than what is needed just for the graphs.

Once we have obtained the position of the DEC curve for the current value of C , by means of the inner loop over values of π_e , we enter an outer loop in which we now change the values of C . We increment C by a fixed variation ΔC , which will characterize the grid

size used for the graphs. We chose to use $\Delta C = 0.005$. Having the new value of C , we repeat the whole search process downward, for the position of the DEC curve. In this next search process we use as the initial value of π_e the last value of this variable obtained in the previous search process. Due to the properties of the DEC curve, which has negative derivative everywhere, this starting value of π_e is guaranteed to be above the DEC curve at the new value of C , but it is much closer to it than an initial value based on the limiting curve, thus making the search more efficient.

The stop criterion for the loop over values of C is that, when the current exponential search downward over π_e concludes, the integration program detect, in its last run, the presence of a divergence. This detection will also result in the creation of a flag file recording the event, to be used by external programs. The presence of a divergence means that the downward search over π_e not only found the DEC curve, but also crossed below the Tooper curve at that value of C . Once the Tooper curve has been crossed or the DEC curve has become sufficiently close to the Tooper curve, there is no longer any chance of finding any point (C, π_e) of the parameter plane that is both below the DEC curve and above the Tooper curve, within the precision limitations with which the graphs are being produced.

3.4 Determination of the Tooper Curve

The determination of the position of the Tooper curve relies on the detection of divergences in the integration process, when one crosses below that curve. We should therefore examine in more detail, before anything else, what happens when we try to run the program below the Tooper curve. The program would usually stop cold when a divergence is detected, but there is an option to still run it for a little while, in order to plot the graph shown in Figure 6, where one can see a representation of the behavior of the differential system when we run below the Tooper curve, in a simple case, with the parameters $n = 1.5$, $C = 1/3$ and $\pi_e = 0.5$. The behavior shown is quite typical. The graph shows all the relevant quantities as functions of the radial variable ξ . The left vertical dotted line, located at $\xi = 1$, is the location at which we start the integration of the differential equation shown in Equation (21), to either side. The integration to the right-hand side proceeds normally and produces a value $\xi_2 \approx 2.9$ for the outer radius, as indicated by the right vertical dotted line. To the right of this point we have the exterior Schwarzschild solution, with $\xi_M \approx 0.97$.

However, the integration to the left-hand side cannot be completed, a value for ξ_1 is never found, and the process has to be interrupted when divergences are detected. As one can see in Figure 6, the function $\gamma(\xi)$ never crosses the ξ axis, and never develops a constant value around the origin. Its derivative $\pi(\xi)$ does not assume a second zero, and instead turns around and diverges quickly to positive infinity. The second derivative $\pi'(\xi)$ diverges even faster to negative infinity. The graphs of the metric functions $\lambda(\xi)$ and $\nu(\xi)$ do not cross one another, and in fact diverge to positive and negative infinity respectively, which is the exact opposite of their usual behavior, when the two graphs do cross, and then diverge in the opposite directions. The dimensionless matter energy density $\bar{\rho}(\xi)$ displays a strong divergence to infinity, and therefore so does $\rho(r)$, thus characterizing a hard singularity of the matter energy density at the origin.

In this simple case it can be determined that $\pi(\xi)$ diverges to infinity faster than $1/\xi$, and therefore that neither $\pi(\xi)$ nor $\bar{\rho}(\xi)$ are integrable functions around the origin. However, due to the singular behavior of the measure factor $\exp[\lambda(\xi) + \nu(\xi)]$ near the origin, it is unclear whether or not this divergence corresponds to either a finite or an infinite total amount of energy around the origin. The detection of the divergence included in the integration program consists of detecting the turnaround of the function $\pi(\xi)$, and therefore the change

of sign of its derivative $\pi'(\xi)$.

3.5 Algorithm for the Tooper Curve

Let us now describe in detail how we determined the position of the Tooper curve. This was done once the DEC curve had already been determined. The exponential search downward towards the Tooper curve proceeded exactly like that for the DEC curve. For each value of n the determination of the Tooper curve starts at the largest value of C for which the position of the DEC curve was successfully determined. At that point, for that value of C , we start the downward search at the value of π_e given by the DEC curve, which is always above the Tooper curve. Since we are looking for a divergence when integrating inward, we integrate the differential system to the left only, towards the origin. If the integration concludes with no divergence, resulting therefore in a definite value for ξ_1 , we decrease the value of π_e by a certain variation $\Delta\pi_e$, and repeat the integration. This proceeds until a divergence is detected, meaning that we are now below the Tooper curve. Once this happens we abort the integration, return π_e to its previous value, decrease the variation $\Delta\pi_e$ by some constant factor, and continues the downward search for the position of the Tooper curve.

Once again this results in a fast exponential search, this time for the position of the Tooper curve, since the variation $\Delta\pi_e$, which represents the distance between the position of the search and the position of the Tooper curve, decreases exponentially fast. Note once again that we can start with a rather large value of $\Delta\pi_e$, since it will be decreased exponentially fast, and again we chose to start with $\Delta\pi_e = 0.1$. Once more the stop criterion for this downward search is the condition that the addition of $\Delta\pi_e$ to π_e no longer change π_e , meaning that the relative precision represented by $\Delta\pi_e/\pi_e$ falls below the precision level at which the search program runs. Since this second search program also runs in double precision mode (64-bit word), this guarantees the localization of the Tooper curve within that double precision level. Naturally, once again the precision of the results of the search is also affected by the precision with which the differential system is integrated. We recall that the integration code runs in quadruple precision mode (128-bit word), and again we chose to use an integration interval of $\Delta\xi = 10^{-5}$. Since the integration program uses the Runge-Kutta fourth-order integration algorithm, once again this results in an excellent level of precision, certainly much greater than what is needed just for the graphs.

Once we have obtained the position of the Tooper curve for the current value of C , by means of the inner loop over values of π_e , we enter an outer loop in which we now change the values of C , which we will now decrease rather than increase. We decrease C by a fixed variation ΔC , which will characterize the grid size used for the graphs. Again we chose to use $\Delta C = 0.005$. Having the new value of C , we repeat the whole search process downward, for the position of the Tooper curve. In this next search process we use as the initial value of π_e the last value of this variable obtained in the previous search process. Due to the properties of the Tooper curve, which has positive derivative everywhere, this starting value of π_e is guaranteed to be above the Tooper curve at the new value of C , but it is much closer to it than an initial value based on the DEC curve, again making the search more efficient. The stop criterion for the loop over values of C is that C would become zero or negative at the next decrement. This can be done by checking whether the current value of C is such that $C \leq \Delta C$. We therefore stop the process of determining the Tooper curve at $C = \Delta C > 0$.

It should be noted that the stop criterion for the loop over π_e may fail in some cases, if we are very close to $C = 0$. This is so because, specially for the case $n = 1.5$, the Tooper

curve approaches $C = 0$ with zero derivative. This tends to make π_e and $\Delta\pi_e$ always commensurate in this case, so that the test that the addition of $\Delta\pi_e$ to π_e fails to change π_e may never succeed. Due to this it was necessary to implement a maximum number of iterations of the loop over π_e , which we chose to be 52. The average number of iterations in order to locate the Tooper curve within the double precision level is a little over 32.

4 Mapping the Observables

On a second phase of the exploration we measured certain observables over the allowed regions, in order to characterize the general behavior of the solutions throughout the regions. These can be considered as diagnostic observables, and the results obtained for them can be seen in Figures 7 through 18. Using them we may, for example, classify the solutions as corresponding to either low-density or high-density distributions of matter, or as being either close to or distant from the formation of an event horizon.

Each successful run of the program produces four fundamental numbers as results that characterize that solution, given by the dimensionfull radii r_1 , r_μ , r_2 and r_M , and hence by the corresponding dimensionless quantities ξ_1 , ξ_μ , ξ_2 and ξ_M . These are all encoded in the function $\gamma(\xi)$; $-\xi_\mu$ is the constant value of $\gamma(\xi)$ within the inner vacuum region, that is, to the left of ξ_1 ; ξ_1 is the point where $\pi(\xi) = \gamma'(\xi)$ becomes zero when integrating inwards; ξ_M is the constant value of $\gamma(\xi)$ within the outer vacuum region, that is, to the right of ξ_2 ; and ξ_2 is the point where $\pi(\xi) = \gamma'(\xi)$ becomes zero when integrating outwards.

All these quantities have well-defined physical meanings, although we believe that in the case of r_μ the complete physical meaning has not yet been completely established; r_1 is the inner radius, or the radial coordinate characterizing the inner vacuum region; r_μ , at least for the time being, has only the meaning of being zero for the Tooper solutions; r_2 is the outer radius, or the radial coordinate characterizing the overall size of the matter distribution; r_M is the Schwarzschild radius, associated to the total mass M and to the total energy Mc^2 of the bound gravitational system. Next we will define our diagnostic observables and describe their main properties.

4.1 Definition of the Observables

We will define, for the purposes of the calculations with the program, three ratios involving the quantities ξ_1 , ξ_μ , ξ_2 and ξ_M , that will have useful properties regarding the characterization of the solutions. All these ratios will assume values within the interval $[0, 1]$. The first one we will name the *Energy Ratio*, which is defined as

$$E_R = \frac{\xi_\mu}{\xi_M + \xi_\mu}. \quad (59)$$

This quantity has the property that it is zero when $\xi_\mu = 0$, and it thus characterizes the Tooper curves. It also has the property that if ξ_μ is very large, with $\xi_\mu \gg \xi_M$, then it approaches the value 1. This $E_R \rightarrow 1$ limit characterizes, therefore, solutions which are *maximally different* from the Tooper solutions. Presumably these are solutions in which other forms of energy are more important than the energy associated to the total asymptotic gravitational mass M , such as, for example, the gravitational binding energy.

The second ratio we will name the *Horizon Ratio*, defined as

$$H_R = \frac{\xi_M}{\xi_2}. \quad (60)$$

The E_R ratio for $n = 1.5$.

Figure 7: The energy ratio E_R for $n = 1.5$. The contours are spaced vertically by 0.06.

The H_R ratio for $n = 1.5$.

Figure 8: The horizon ratio H_R for $n = 1.5$. The contours are spaced vertically by 0.06.

The Q_R ratio for $n = 1.5$.

Figure 9: The quantum ratio Q_R for $n = 1.5$. The contours are spaced vertically by 0.06.

Since all our solutions here have the property that $\xi_M < \xi_2$, this quantity is always smaller than 1. However, there may be limits in which it approaches 1. This quantity has the property that for very low-density objects, for which $\xi_M \ll \xi_2$, it approaches zero. Therefore, this observable indicates low-density solutions when it is small, as is the case near the Tooper curves for small values of C . On the other hand, if ξ_M and ξ_2 become very close, then this ratio approaches 1. In this case one approaches a situation in which an event horizon forms at the position ξ_2 , according to the exterior Schwarzschild solution, which is valid outside ξ_2 , and which in this limit acquires the well-known coordinate singularity at ξ_2 . Therefore this ratio discriminates between low-density and high-density solutions, including the onset of black hole solutions, in the $H_R \rightarrow 1$ limit.

The third ratio we will name the *Quantum Ratio*, defined as

$$Q_R = \frac{\xi_1}{\xi_2}. \quad (61)$$

Clearly the name chosen requires some explanation. This has the property that it is zero if $\xi_1 = 0$, in which case we have solutions for filled spheres, instead of shells. In this way, it characterizes the Tooper curves just like E_R , but since there are many other solutions for which $\xi_1 \ll \xi_2$, even if $\xi_1 \neq 0$, this diagnostic is not particularly helpful.

On the other hand, if we recall that all the matter in the system is located between ξ_1 and ξ_2 , we see that when the inner radius approaches the outer radius the proper volume containing the matter shrinks to zero, resulting in infinite localized matter energy densities. If we consider the dimensionless radial coordinate ξ , we have that in this case the coordinate thickness $\xi_2 - \xi_1$ of the shell goes to zero, so that the corresponding proper length will eventually become commensurate with the correlation lengths (or wavelengths) of the fields associated to the particles of matter within the shell. In this case it is to be expected that the quantum behavior of the matter will prevent this thickness from decreasing any further. In other words, it is reasonable to expect that the quantum properties of the matter will prevent the shell from degenerating into a true two-dimensional surface. Therefore, the limit $Q_R \rightarrow 1$ indicates situations in which the quantum properties of matter come into play.

4.2 Behavior of the Observables

Graphs of the observables E_R , H_R and Q_R can be seen in Figures 7 through 18, for all the values of n used. In these graphs we chose to use a step for C given by $\Delta C = 0.01$, and a step for π_e given by $\Delta \pi_e = 0.1$. As one can see in the graphs, the qualitative behavior of the ratios E_R , H_R and Q_R as functions of C and π_e is quite similar for all the values of n explored, thus indicating that the same is at least qualitatively true for ξ_1 , ξ_μ , ξ_2 and ξ_M as well. In all the parameter plane graphs shown in Figures 1 through 4 there are essentially the same regions with the same specific properties for the solutions, with the possible exception of the rather small anomalous region for the larger values of C , in the case $n = 3.0$.

This particular small region is characterized by very large values of ξ_2 , and hence by very small values of H_R and Q_R . In this region the program takes a very long time to find the value of ξ_2 , and thus sometimes overtaxes the available computer resources. The integration interval used was $\Delta \xi = 10^{-5}$ in all cases except the case $n = 3.0$, in which we found it necessary to use $\Delta \xi = 10^{-6}$.

Let us start by describing how each one of the three ratios behaves along the allowed regions. The ratio E_R goes to zero at the Tooper curves, as expected, thus pinpointing the locations of these curves. It seems to increase towards 1 as we enter the asymptotic parts of

The E_R ratio for $n = 2.0$.

Figure 10: The energy ratio E_R for $n = 2.0$. The contours are spaced vertically by 0.06.

The H_R ratio for $n = 2.0$.

Figure 11: The horizon ratio H_R for $n = 2.0$. The contours are spaced vertically by 0.06.

The Q_R ratio for $n = 2.0$.

Figure 12: The quantum ratio Q_R for $n = 2.0$. The contours are spaced vertically by 0.06.

the allowed regions, with $C \rightarrow 0$ and $\pi_e \rightarrow \infty$, thus indicating that ξ_μ becomes very large as we travel deeper into these regions.

The ratio H_R has values smaller than 1, but sometimes not close to zero, over the whole length of the Tooper curves, and very small values near the point $C = 0$. This means that there may be solutions with significant overall matter density on the Tooper curve, specially in the case $N = 1.5$. There are also solutions with very small such density near $C = 0$. This ratio also seems to increase towards 1 as we enter the asymptotic parts of the allowed regions, with $C \rightarrow 0$ and $\pi_e \rightarrow \infty$, thus indicating that as we travel deeper into these regions we proceed towards high overall densities and the possible formation of event horizons.

The ratio Q_R is zero over the whole length of the Tooper curves, thus indicating that we have $\xi_1 = 0$ there, as expected. It is also either zero or very small over most of the allowed regions, thus indicating that in general we have $\xi_1 \ll \xi_2$. It only becomes significantly larger than zero for small C , near the π_e axis. Also, it can be seen that it increases slowly as we travel into the asymptotic regions. This indicates that on limits for which $C \rightarrow 0$ and $\pi_e \rightarrow \infty$ within these regions the quantum effects of the matter may eventually come into play.

4.3 The General Picture

Examining what happens in each part of the allowed regions, some general conclusions can be formulated. To begin with, over or near the Tooper curves we never approach the formation of event horizons. The same is true for the parts of the DEC curves shown in the graphs. Another way to say this is to point out that for finite and non-zero values of C the solutions never form event horizons, and that for the larger values of C they never get anywhere even close to that.

For each value of n the asymptotic region, where $C \rightarrow 0$ and $\pi_e \rightarrow \infty$, is the one region where we can approach the formation of an event horizon. This is also the region where we get extremely high overall matter densities, since this density increases as we enter more and more deeply into these asymptotic regions. The detailed exploration of the black hole limits in these asymptotic regions would require a different numerical approach, with a whole new set of runs, and due to this will have to be postponed to a subsequent paper.

The two basic properties of the Tooper curves, that over them we have $\xi_1 = 0$ and $\xi_\mu = 0$, are confirmed by our exploration. Very low density objects seem to exist mostly near the origin, for very small values of both C and π_e . That seems to be the realm of the main-sequence stars. It may be possible to find somewhat similar solutions in the small mostly regular region located beyond the anomalous region of the case $n = 3.0$, but at this point it is not really clear what the true character of these particular solutions might be. Below the Tooper curves, that is for very small values of π_e , given some values of n and C , as well as for sufficiently large C , there are no solutions at all. The upper limit for C is somewhere between 0.5 and 0.8 depending on the value of n .

Close to the DEC curves we have extremely relativistic matter, with overall matter densities that vary from significant to very high. Since the matter involved in this solution is a simple ideal gas of massive particles, there is only one way in which its behavior can violate the dynamic precepts of Relativity, namely the speed of its particles either reaching or surpassing the speed of light. Therefore, it is to be expected that in this region the speed of sound in the gas is close to the speed of light, and also that their average speed of thermal agitation is close to the speed of light. This implies truly immense thermal energies and temperatures, and it can be imagined how this may also help to prevent the formation

The E_R ratio for $n = 2.5$.

Figure 13: The energy ratio E_R for $n = 2.5$. The contours are spaced vertically by 0.06.

The H_R ratio for $n = 2.5$.

Figure 14: The horizon ratio H_R for $n = 2.5$. The contours are spaced vertically by 0.06.

The Q_R ratio for $n = 2.5$.

Figure 15: The quantum ratio Q_R for $n = 2.5$. The contours are spaced vertically by 0.06.

of event horizons. It is important to emphasize here that these are *relativistically* high temperatures, orders of magnitude above what would be considered as high temperatures in the realm of stars and other celestial objects, even for the hottest such objects. Therefore, close enough to the DEC curves these cases seem to be far beyond any objects that one could ever hope to find in nature.

5 Application to Astrophysics

Let us now discuss how one can use this family of solutions in order to obtain the solutions for definite objects, say with given mass and outer radius. To start with, let us assume that we want the solution for an object of mass M , and therefore with Schwarzschild radius r_M . The problem poses itself of what values of the free parameters n , C and π_e should be used in order to obtain a solution with the required properties. Note that the value of M is not directly involved in the choice of these dimensionless parameters. We will see that there is no single solution to this first problem, but rather a significant amount of arbitrary choice involved.

Regarding the value of n , one can either choose an appropriate value of n to represent the type of thermodynamic behavior of the matter involved, or one can construct, for example, a two-layer solution, with layers that are connected by means of appropriate interface boundary conditions at a certain interface between two different layers of matter, with different thermodynamic behaviors. A two-layer model of a star with a radiative inner layer, say with $n = 3.0$, and an isentropic outer layer, say with $n = 1.5$, comes to mind. Putting aside for now this more complex alternatives, let us just assume, for the purposes of this discussion, that we simply chose some value of n for a single-layer solution.

For *any* values of C and π_e that one chooses to run the program with, assuming only that the point (C, π_e) is within the allowed region of the parameter plane for the value of n to be used, there will result some definite values for ξ_1 , ξ_μ , ξ_2 and ξ_M . If we have a required value of r_M , then we can at once determine the parameter r_0 , for any values of C and π_e whatsoever, since we have that

$$r_0 = \frac{r_M}{\xi_M}. \quad (62)$$

This determines the position r_0 of the inflection point of $\beta(r)$, and therefore the position of the point of maximum of $\beta'(r)$. Having determined r_0 , we can now determine all other relevant dimensionfull quantities, since we have that

$$r_1 = \xi_1 r_0, \quad (63)$$

$$r_\mu = \xi_\mu r_0, \quad (64)$$

$$r_2 = \xi_2 r_0. \quad (65)$$

We therefore see that there are solutions for all possible positive values of r_M , and hence of M . The fact that the parameter r_M was factored out of the system, when we wrote it in terms of dimensionless parameters, betrays the existence of a scaling transformation among the solutions, parametrized by the value of r_M . Given n , any point (C, π_e) in the allowed region of the corresponding parameter plane corresponds in fact to an infinite set of similar solutions, for all possible values of r_M , and hence of M . At this point we may also determine the polytropic constant K , since we have that

$$K = C (\kappa r_0^2)^{1/n}, \quad (66)$$

The E_R ratio for $n = 3.0$.

Figure 16: The energy ratio E_R for $n = 3.0$. The contours are spaced vertically by 0.06.

The H_R ratio for $n = 3.0$.

Figure 17: The horizon ratio H_R for $n = 3.0$. The contours are spaced vertically by 0.06.

The Q_R ratio for $n = 3.0$.

Figure 18: The quantum ratio Q_R for $n = 3.0$. The contours are spaced vertically by 0.06.

where $\kappa = 8\pi G/c^4$. If we want to have a certain given value, say, for r_2 , then it will be necessary to explore the parameter plane in order to find a point (C, π_e) that yields the required values of both M and r_2 . And again there will be more than just one such point, since we still have two free parameters to determine.

Note that, given n , since we still have the two free parameters C and π_e , we have open to us the possibility of choosing freely one more property of the object under study, besides the mass and the outer radius, and still have the means to find the corresponding solutions. For example, we may require that $r_\mu = 0$, which will put us squarely on top of the Tooper curve. But a more interesting alternative does immediately come to mind, that of choosing the surface temperature of the object. If this was done, it could result in a complete map of the relations between mass, outer radius and surface temperature of stars, which might even be directly verifiable against observations. But of course it would probably be far more compelling to do this in the context of a two-layer model for the stars.

Given the way in which one has to use the program in order to obtain solutions with specific given properties, it would be useful to have approximate numerical functions implementing the quantities $(\xi_1, \xi_\mu, \xi_2, \xi_M)$ as functions of n , C and π_e . These could then be used to solve numerically for the parameters needed in order to obtain, for example, some required mass and outer radius. Even the function data generated in order to produce the graphs shown in Figures 7 through 18, or the graphs themselves, could, at least in principle, be used for that purpose. For example, if one requires M to be, say, the mass of the Sun, and r_2 to be its outer radius, this determines the value of the ratio $H_R(C, \pi_e) = r_M/r_2$, which in turn determines a certain curve on the (C, π_e) parameter plane. Running the program at any point on this curve will generate a solution for the required values of M and r_2 . This means, of course, that we are still able to require some given value for one more characteristic of the Sun, such as its surface temperature.

6 Further Analysis

Here we will present some further points of analysis, mostly of a qualitative nature, of the solutions and their properties, and also point out some of their limitations. Most of these observations and conclusions depend only on the results that were already presented in [1]. There are several qualitative conclusions that can be drawn without any further lengthy and detailed calculations. For example, regarding the inner vacuum and the singularities at the center, there are a few relevant observations that should be made here. Also some observations can be made about the issue of the surface temperature and of the emission of electromagnetic energy by the matter. Some of these topics may be of interest for the potential applications of the solutions to problems in astrophysics.

Cosmic Censorship: The first relevant observation regarding the central singularities is that, strictly speaking, these solutions violate the hypothesis of “cosmic censorship”, since most of them contain at the center a hard, invariant curvature singularity that is *not* protected by an event horizon. However, this hard conclusion is somewhat softened by the fact that these singularities are repulsive rather than attractive, and therefore do not lead to infinite concentrations of matter at the center, which has always been the perceived central physical problem with such unprotected hard singularities. So long as one considers that the central objective of this famous hypothesis is to prevent the possibility of the direct observation of a hard geometrical singularity associated to the infinite concentration of matter at a single point, one can see that this objective can still be achieved if that hypothesis is simply limited to attractive singularities.

Singularity Classification: The second relevant observation regarding the central singularities is that the very fact that these singularities are repulsive rather than attractive means that the classification of singularities in General Relativity is incomplete, since it makes no mention of the attractive or repulsive nature of the singularities, or in fact establishes any distinction between these two cases, or even takes into any account at all this characteristic of the singularities. The very definition of the singularities in General Relativity is usually based solely on differential-geometry concepts and considerations, while the classification as either attractive or repulsive has a more markedly physical character. This physical characteristic is based mainly on the concept of time, and it is the temporal component $\exp[2\nu(r)]$ of the metric that dictates it, by determining the either attractive or repulsive behavior of the gravitational field around the singularity.

Interior Gravity: These solutions also contradict the widely held belief that in General Relativity an empty cavity within any spherically symmetric distribution of matter necessarily contains no gravitational field. What we are led to verify here is that, while this is indeed the case in Newtonian gravity, it is not true in Einstein's theory of gravitation. In fact, the inner vacuum region of either gaseous or liquid shell solutions does contain a non-trivial gravitational field, albeit one that is repulsive with respect to the origin, thus establishing a counter-example to this widely held belief. It is important to note that this interior gravitational field represents the *outward* gravitational attraction towards the shell of matter that surrounds that inner vacuum region, and should not be confused in any way with any form of repulsive gravitation between material particles.

Since the presence of the central repulsive singularity within the inner cavity, and the existence of the associated interior repulsive gravitational field, have now been observed in many different cases, not only for liquids and gases, with a variety of different thermodynamic behaviors, but also in numerical studies of neutron stars [7,8] using a Chandrasekhar-style equation of state [9], it seems very unlikely that this situation is just a peculiar quirk of some particular cases. Although, in so far as the author is aware, there is currently no rigorous proof of this, it does seem that this is a general and fundamental property of Einstein's theory of gravitation.

In our case here the central singularity and the gravitational field within the inner vacuum region can only be made to vanish if we make $r_\mu = 0$, which is only true for the particular case of the Tooper solutions. Only in these cases it holds that $r_\mu = 0$, and then it is indeed true that within the whole inner vacuum region $\lambda(r)$ reduces to zero and $\nu(r)$ reduces to a negative constant, thus producing a situation in which there is no real gravitational field, but only a constant overall blue shift with respect to radial infinity. However, we have shown for both the case of gaseous matter in [1], and for the case of liquid matter in [2], that in these cases we also necessarily have that $r_1 = 0$, so that the inner vacuum regions reduces to a single point, and therefore in these cases there is no central cavity left at all.

Emission of Radiation: If a comparison with real stars is intended, then it must be remembered that these solutions are static, while more realistic solutions would be only approximately static, since stars lose energy, even if very slowly, due to the outward emission of electromagnetic radiation at the outer surface of the matter, that is, at or near the outer matter-vacuum interface. This will result in an approximately constant outward flux of radiation, all the way to radial infinity. So long as this flux, multiplied by some observationally relevant time interval, is small compared to the total energy stored in the star, which is almost always the case, the solutions are still good approximations of the real

phenomena. However, we must now remember that in these shell solutions we have two surfaces, the external one at r_2 and an internal one at r_1 , so that there will be emission of radiation inward as well.

While the outward radiation propagates to infinity in a fairly steady stream, the inward radiation enters a cavity with finite volume, so that the radiation will accumulate there, as a gas of photons, until thermal equilibrium is reached. Clearly there will be no long-term loss of energy due to the inward radiation. Note that the thermal equilibrium within the inner cavity does not mean that the gas of photons will have the same temperature everywhere within it, since this temperature will be modulated along the radial coordinate r by the radial red and blue shifts implied by the fact that $\nu(r)$ is not a constant. Starting at a certain temperature at the inner surface, the temperature will fall all the way to zero at the singularity, if we do not take into account the diffraction effects of long-wavelength radiation around the singularity.

It is interesting to observe that sufficiently near the central singularity all incoming radiation, of any original frequency, will acquire very long wavelengths, due to the very large red shift undergone while approaching the origin. This low-frequency radiation will then be utterly incapable of interacting directly with a point-like singularity, and will instead diffract around it. This shows how the mere existence of the point-like repulsive central singularity may not actually lead to any disastrous consequences at all for the physics.

Temperature of Emission: The question now rises of what is the relation between the temperatures at the outer and inner surfaces. In order to discuss this we must first recall how the photosphere surface of a star is defined. Given a certain frequency of electromagnetic radiation, the radial position where the plasma has sufficiently low density $\rho(r)$ to become transparent to that frequency defines the position of the visible surface of the star, at that frequency. The relevant condition is therefore that $\rho(r)$ attains a certain small value determined by the wavelength of the light and by the electronic density of the plasma. This is based on the opaque-transparent transition in a plasma.

Now, from the interface boundary conditions we know that $P(r)$ and $\rho(r)$ are zero at both r_1 and r_2 , so that any condition that $\rho(r)$ be sufficiently small will be satisfied both close to and to the left of the position r_2 of the outer surface, and close to and to the right of the position r_1 of the inner surface. This is true for all frequencies, and therefore will be valid for a black-body spectrum of frequencies emitted from a fairly thin layer near either surface of the star, at the temperature of that surface, both from the outer surface and from the inner surface. Therefore we may conclude that the emission of the radiation occurs at exactly the same local temperature for both the outer and inner photospheres.

Blue and Red Shifts: In the case of the outgoing radiation to the outer vacuum region there is some finite amount of red shift as the radiation streams away to radial infinity, while the intensity of the radiation falls with the distance much more than what is implied just by that red shift. However, in the case of the ingoing radiation into the inner vacuum region there will be an essentially infinite amount of red shift as the radiation streams towards the center, and an equally large amount of blue shift when it streams back out again. Within the inner cavity we will eventually attain thermal equilibrium, with equal amounts of ingoing and outgoing fluxes of energy at each radial position. The intensity of these fluxes of energy at any given radial position will have their maximum thermodynamically defined black-body values for the temperature at that position.

It is interesting to note that the amount of red shift with respect to the asymptotic flat space at radial infinity is the same for both surfaces of the matter. This is so because

we have that $\nu(r_1) = \nu(r_2)$, as is shown by Equations (15) and (17), and by the fact that both $\beta'(r_1)$ and $\beta'(r_2)$ are zero. The same is true for the two photospheres, since from Equations (13), (15) and (17) one can see that $\nu(r)$ can be written as a function of only $\rho(r)$. Therefore, when $\rho(r)$ satisfies the same transparency-transition condition at the two photosphere surfaces, having therefore the same value at both surfaces, it follows that $\nu(r)$ will have the same value in both photosphere surfaces as well, thus leading to the same amount of red shift with respect to radial infinity.

Radiation Back-Reaction: It is important to point out that the solutions we present here are incomplete in one respect, that being the fact that they do not take into account the outward flux of electromagnetic radiation from the gas, or the density of electromagnetic energy within the cavity, in terms of their possible influence back on the metric and associated geometry. Surely the solutions can still be good approximations of the phenomena so long as the temperature at which the radiation is emitted is not extremely high, thus staying well below relativistic speeds of thermal agitation of the gas, and so long as the energy fluxes of emitted radiation are not too large.

This certainly represents no problem near the Tooper curves, and for solutions representing main sequence stars, with non-relativistic surface temperatures. And probably it is also not a problem for solutions that are very close to black-hole solutions, due to the severe red shift that the emitted radiation undergoes in these cases, thus limiting the energy radiated. However, it can and probably will be a problem for the relativistically extreme solutions near the DEC curves, where the matter may display deep relativistic behavior, possibly leading to high densities of electromagnetic energy within the inner cavity.

Other Temperature Considerations: One important topic that is still missing from our explorations so far is that of the detailed study of the temperature of the gas in the context of these solutions. As we discussed above in this Section, the surface temperatures of the outer and inner surfaces are the same, and in general they are comparatively low, so that very high temperatures may occur only deep within the shells of matter. Nuclear reactions require such very high temperatures, and therefore may occur only near the middle of the matter shells, and not at the central regions of the objects, even if they were filled with some thin gas.

The relation shown in Equation (10), if compared to the basic equation of state of an ideal gas, betrays the fact that the quantity $F(r)$ is directly related to the temperature of the gas, at least for non-relativistic temperatures. In fact, from Equation (10) we can see that the DEC, as expressed in Equation (50), can be stated simply as $F(r) \leq 1$. Since according to Equation (9) the quantity $F(r)$ is proportional to a positive power of $\rho(r)$, it is maximum where $\rho(r)$ is maximum, and therefore the temperature should also be maximum where $\rho(r)$ is maximum. This is always somewhat to the left of the point where the function $\beta'(r)$ has its maximum. This represents therefore the position where the nuclear reactions within the star are most likely to occur, somewhere between the inner interface at r_1 and the inflection point r_e of $\beta(r)$, where $\beta'(r)$ has its maximum value.

As we discussed before, the value of the quantity $F(r)$ at the radial position where the plasma has sufficiently low density and thus becomes transparent essentially defines the position of the visible surface of the star, as well as its local temperature and hence its local apparent color. The temperature and apparent color as seen from radial infinity can then be obtained via a red-shift calculation, using the value of $\nu(r)$ at that surface. This would then allow us to determine the solutions for given mass, external radius and apparent color of a star. Since, given the number of available free parameters in the solutions, these three

quantities would completely determine the solution, we should then be able to determine all other quantities of interest, including for example r_1 , r_μ and the maximum values of the energy density and of the internal temperature.

7 Conclusions

Unlike the Schwarzschild, Reissner-Nordström and Kerr-Newman solutions of the Einstein field equations, which represent static vacua and are valid only in the exterior region of a spherically or axially symmetric material object, the family of solutions for polytropic matter that we presented in [1] and explored here consists of static and spherically symmetric solutions valid over the whole extent of the three-dimensional spatial manifold, for all values of r . This makes them of particular interest as models for astrophysical objects, in both the low-density case, such as main sequence stars, and in the high-density case, particularly in the case of black holes or objects close to them in terms of their exterior geometry.

In the previous paper [1], in which the solutions were presented, we also presented a few examples of such solutions, both with low and high matter energy densities, including both the functions that represent the matter and the functions that represent the geometry. However, even in its dimensionless form, this is a rather large three-parameter set of solutions, and of course due to space limitations we could give only a few illustrative examples. In this paper we explored a significant part of this three-dimensional parameter space, for arbitrary values of the mass M , in order to establish both the existence of specific solutions and some of the main properties of these solutions.

We did this for a small set of values of the polytropic index n that includes some of those which are most often used in astrophysics. These are usually either integer or half-integer, but it should be pointed out that neither the solutions nor the numerical program have any limitations regarding the use of real numbers for n , other than that n must be strictly positive and finite. The other free dimensionless parameters of the family of solutions are the dimensionless polytropic constant C and the maximum value π_e of the necessarily non-negative function $\pi(\xi)$, which is the derivative of the function $\gamma(\xi)$, which in turn is the central mathematical element of the whole family of solutions.

The existence of the solutions hinges on the existence of the radial positions r_1 and r_2 , that is, on the existence of values of r at which the matter energy density $\rho(r)$ becomes exactly zero. These are also the positions ξ_1 and ξ_2 where the derivative $\pi(\xi)$ of the function $\gamma(\xi)$ becomes exactly zero. We found that many such solutions do in fact exist, in various different regions of the (C, π_e) parameter planes, for each value of n that was tried. These solutions span a large space of possibilities, from very low-density solutions to very high-density ones. Also, it seems that there exist solutions that are as close as one may wish to situations in which an event horizon exists, but this sector still requires further exploration and analysis.

Besides examining the question of the existence of the solutions, we also examined the behavior of the matter using the Dominant Energy Condition (DEC). This condition determines whether or not the matter associated to the solutions behaves in a physically acceptable way. We found that there are many solutions for which this condition is satisfied. Combining the condition of existence and the DEC we located the allowed regions of the parameter planes, where all physically acceptable solutions are located. These regions exist only within finite intervals of values of C , but extend to arbitrarily large values of π_e .

For all values of n examined here these allowed regions of the parameter planes have asymptotic sub-regions, for very large values of π_e and very small values of C , in which

we are led to surmise that solutions representing black holes, or solutions that are in some sense close to them, are located. It was possible to identify families of curves within the allowed regions, that extend indefinitely within these asymptotic regions, and that have the property of approaching black-hole limits. Of course these infinite asymptotic regions will have to be explored using numerical approaches other than mapping the complete regions, and thus such an effort will have to be postponed to a subsequent paper, to be dedicated to this issue.

Besides these asymptotic regions, there are other small regions which might deserve further scrutiny, as was pointed out in the text. And we should not forget that the cases with $n < 1$, which promise to be significantly different from the ones explored here, are still to be examined in any significant amount of detail. In fact, there are many possible extensions and generalizations of the exploration presented here, as well as different studies that could be done with these solutions. Of particular interest would be the study of the temperature in these solutions, specially the observable surface temperature.

However, in all fairness we would like to finish by pointing out that perhaps the most significant limitation of this family of solutions is a rather fundamental one, namely that they do not include the angular momentum of rotating objects. The extension of these solutions to that case remains as a very significant and important open challenge.

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Data Availability Statement

Data sharing not applicable to this article as no experimental or observational datasets were generated or analyzed during the current study.

Conflict of Interest Statement

The author hereby certifies that there are no actual or potential conflicts of interest in relation to this article.

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